

**D5.5 - FINAL REPORT ON POLICY
RECOMMENDATIONS AND GUIDELINES FOR THE
SUSTAINABLE TRANSITION**

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Authors	Harry Schindler (DBFZ)
Reviewers	Gülşah Yılan (UNIT), Edvin Andreasson (KE), Gabor Mester (PC)

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analyzed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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#	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
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2	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
3	KNOWLEDGE SRL	KE	IT
4	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC	SK
5	DBFZ DEUTSCHES BIOMASSEFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GEMEINNÜTZIGE GMBH	DBFZ	DE
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10	BUNDESANSTALT FUER MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND -PRÜFUNG	BAM	DE
11	FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIÓN DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGÉTICOS	CIRCE	ES

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Creating a Circular Bio-Based Economy (CBBE) is associated with several obstacles, including market challenges such as the lack of competitiveness of sustainable products. In addition, policy challenges have to be overcome, such as the high complexity of the transition and unintended side effects. SUSTRACK illustrates a possible approach on how to navigate through this complexity and create consistent policy solutions.

This approach requires, first, a careful assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the dominant type of policy intervention - direct regulation or market-based instruments. A market-based policy approach is often better suited to deal with the complexity and limit administrative burdens of the transition. However, direct regulation meets higher acceptance from stakeholders and can induce change where politically feasible pricing instruments or subsidies are ineffective. Depending on the weight policy makers assign to the strengths and weaknesses, one or another policy pathway can be preferable. Regarding individual policy instruments, the most promising options are:

- subsidies to support innovative solutions,
- quotas for the use of sustainable feedstocks in combination with
- sustainability criteria for material uses of biomass and
- a carbon price for fossil feedstocks and low-value biomass uses.

Depending on the characteristics of individual economic sectors and stakeholder preferences, this basic policy mix allows for a customisation for different sectors:

- In the textiles sector, market-based instruments such as a tax on fossil feedstocks and fast fashion, in combination with a “Green VAT”, could lead the transition.
- In the chemicals sector, combining a quota for non-fossil feedstocks with a pollution tax can be used to initiate change despite high transition costs (quota) and to cope with the high dynamics of a market that continuously produces novel substances (tax).
- In the (non-packaging) plastics sector, the similar challenge of high transition costs and complexity can be addressed likewise with a mix of instruments that effectively drive change (eco-design criteria and quota for recycled materials) and improve the competitiveness of sustainable solutions for circular and bio-based solutions that elude direct regulation.
- In the construction sector, financial support (for innovation and carbon storage in bio-materials) could be combined with standards for building and demolishing infrastructures.

To account for varying conditions in the EU member states, the EU might consider creating differentiated levels of ambition or providing targeted support to less advanced economies. It should also be taken into account that EU member states vary in their success regarding compliance with environmental targets or target trajectories, for example, regarding protecting and enhancing carbon sinks in the land use sector LULUCF. This again may justify additional EU support for these sinks or require restrictions in regard to policies supporting the use of (forest) biomass. Varying progress in terms of waste management infrastructure is another factor to consider when, for example, setting quotas for using recycled materials.

A process with the scope and depth of the CBBE is also likely to impact overarching economic variables such as economic growth and employment. While the transition may positively affect growth in the long run under certain conditions, stagnation or even negative growth may occur along the way, possibly requiring additional policy interventions. Furthermore, the CBBE transition may lead to substantial shifts in employment away from manufacturing to other sectors. Policy makers should smooth this transition, e.g., with respective programs for requalification. In addition, the modelled transition scenarios show that a CBBE is likely to increase demand for biomass. To align this effect with efforts to protect biodiversity or other ecological sustainability targets, strategies to cultivate additional biomass in line with such targets are required. Alternatively, or in addition to this, measures to reallocate biomass from low- to high-value uses can support the sustainability of the transition.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
CBBE	Circular Bio-Based Economy
D	Deliverable
ETS	Emissions Trading System
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GVA	Gross Value Added
LULUCF	Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises

1. INTRODUCTION: WHAT ARE THE CHALLENGES

1.1 Background

The EU intends to transition toward a circular and bio-based economy (CBBE). This transformation seeks to phase out fossil resources and end the make-use-dispose type of economy. Next to using biomass, “R-strategies” such as reduce, reuse and recycle constitute key measures. The transition shall contribute to climate protection, competitiveness, supply security, sustainable resource management and food security. To support policymakers in this transition, the EU Horizon research project SUSTRACK identifies policy priorities. The project focuses on the sectors construction, plastics, chemicals and textiles.

This report derives policy recommendations and guidelines for the CBBE transition, based on all tasks carried out in SUSTRACK and the respective results. Previous work packages have analysed limits of the linear fossil-based economy and barriers for the CBBE transition (D1.1, D1.3), created a monitoring system for measuring transition progress (D2.4), selected and analysed major features of CBBE key sectors (D3.4), modelled the economic and ecological effects of the transition (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3), reviewed policy options and collected feedback from stakeholders (D5.3, D5.4).

1.2 Challenges

Making policies to turn the EU economy into a CBBE requires policymakers to be aware of the different challenges associated with the transition. A clear understanding of transition challenges is the foundation of effective and consistent policy solutions. CBBE transition challenges can be divided into two categories:

- **Tier 1 challenges** are obstacles that hinder the **market penetration** of circular or bio-based products and practices, such as the lack of competitiveness or cultural barriers.
- **Tier 2 challenges** refer to **obstacles at the policy level**, i.e. barriers that hamper making policies to overcome tier 1 challenges, for example, trade-offs between different policy goals.

In SUSTRACK, almost 200 barriers have been identified via literature review and stakeholder discussions. Via different methods, key barriers were highlighted. Interestingly, a large proportion of these key barriers are tier 2 challenges. This means that, next to obvious tier 1 challenges such as a lack of competitiveness, the process of policy making must be critically examined and possibly adjusted to accelerate the CBBE transition. The following sections briefly outline both tier challenges. Tier 2 challenges are outlined in more detail because solving these policy-related challenges is a prerequisite for overcoming tier 1 obstacles (i.e., creating effective policies). Details on the methods used to identify and cluster the barriers can be found in previous SUSTRACK deliverables (D1.1-D1.3 and D5.3).

1.2.1 Tier 1: Market challenges

SUSTRACK has collected a wide range of different types of tier 1 barriers, categorized into economic, environmental, social, cultural, structural and technological barriers. Via stakeholder engagement and multi-criteria decision analysis, the large number of barriers has been narrowed down in SUSTRACK to 14 key barriers, that are transversal across various clusters (see table 10 in D1.3). Applying categories of market challenges from sustainability transition literature (Jaffe et al. 2005; Aalbers et al. 2013; van den Bergh 2013), the key challenges for policymakers can be summarised in the following way:

Challenge 1-1: Low competitiveness

Among the large number of challenges, the lack of competitiveness of circular and bio-based products (or practices) stands out. This lack comes in various shapes, such as high investment costs, high operating costs, lack of public funding and private investments, competitive advantages of fossil-based products and lack of incentives for consumer behaviour change. The low competitiveness can be explained by different market failures, such as externalities related to fossil fuels (Stern 2007), biomass (LINTUNEN and UUSIVUORI 2016), other natural resources (Gaudet 2007; Kronenberg 2008) or the use of the environment as a sink for waste and emissions (Baumol and Oates 2005).

Challenge 1-2: Information barriers

In addition to the cost barrier, information challenges impede the CBBE transition. This includes the lack of information but also misinformation, e.g., in the form of greenwashing. On the consumer side, missing information can take the form of low awareness regarding the environmental benefits of more sustainable products. Sometimes, not the lack but a high amount of information constitutes the challenge, for example, when a large variety of sustainability labels confuses consumers and undermines their trust in this type of instrument.

Challenge 1-3: Lock-in effects

Even if circular and bio-based products were competitive and labelled with all relevant information in an easily digestible way, change towards the CBBE might still be slow due to structural inertia. The literature and stakeholders stress physical infrastructure that is designed according to the properties of linear fossil-based products and a “make-use-dispose” culture. For example, insufficient infrastructure for separate waste collection often poses a barrier to high-quality recycling. Another structural challenge concerns social lock-ins, i.e., norms, customs and habits. This includes being familiar with using certain technologies, because switching to novel and more sustainable technologies requires costly processes of learning or adaptation (e.g., switching from fossil to bio-based feedstocks in the chemical industry).

Challenge 1-4: Lack of technology

Especially in regard to the circularity dimension of the CBBE, one key challenge lies in the increasing complexity of composite materials. This includes the use of various chemical additives intended to modify product properties (appearance, durability, etc.). This material complexity makes recycling and reusing products more difficult or even hazardous. In terms of policy challenges, this can be understood as a technology barrier, i.e. the lack of technologies to either produce goods with desired properties in a less complex and toxic way, or a lack of technologies to recycle complex products in a low-cost and safe manner.

This leads to the following first key policy recommendation:

Policy recommendation 1: To support the CBBE transition, a combination of policies has to be established that a) improve the competitiveness of sustainable products, b) provide credible and digestible information, c) address lock-in effects and push technology development.

1.2.2 Tier 2: Policy challenges

Policy makers are regularly confronted with challenging policy tasks. Creating a CBBE, however, constitutes an extraordinary task because of the vast scope and considerable depth of the process. Both characteristics contribute to the high complexity of the policy challenge. This can be illustrated by comparing the CBBE transition to the energy transition: The latter basically intends to replace three (intermediate/final) goods - fossil-based electricity, heat/cold and transport fuels, all of which are based on fossil oil, gas or coal. By contrast, the CBBE directly addresses tens of thousands of products made out dozens of minerals, metals and other resources (scope). While the energy transition may have forced manufacturers to switch their energy input in the production process, the CBBE transition requires them to reconsider all material inputs, possibly the production process and the product design (depth). In addition to this, the transition can fundamentally alter the role of consumers in markets: Instead of buying a new product from a company, they may increasingly choose to repair an existing product, or they might buy a second-hand product from other private households or companies specialised in second-hand products. They might also increasingly engage in selling their own used products, thereby becoming more of a supplier instead of being a consumer only. Such practices might increasingly become a part of our everyday life and change the way we choose and deal with products.

Creating effective and consistent policies for a process of this magnitude and complexity poses substantial challenges:

Challenge 2-1: Complex policy targets

Circular economy and bioeconomy are conceptual tools to reduce complexity. They help us to translate abstract sustainability goals, such as UN SDGs, into actionable policies such as recycling quotas (Kirchherr et al. 2017). Still, measures like recycling or biomass use remain partially abstract and challenging themselves. For example, we know that recycling is part of a more sustainable world - yet, it is unclear how much recycling is actually sustainable. Pushing recycling to technical limits may consume more resources and create more waste and pollution than it helps to reduce (Baumol 1977; Tian et al. 2020). Given the potentially large number of resources required for making a new product vs. for recycling a used product (various natural resources, energy, machinery, labour, chemicals, financial capital, etc.), it can be difficult to decide when recycling is indeed better (more sustainable) than using virgin raw materials. A similar challenge is related to the use of biomass in a bioeconomy: While replacing some fossil-based products with bio-based products can contribute to reducing GHG emissions, substituting large shares of fossil-based materials with biomass is likely to increase emissions (Hurmekoski et al. 2023; Hu et al. 2025). Deciding how much biomass can be used to create positive climate impacts is, again, highly complex and controversial (Cowie et al. 2021). Hence, defining policy targets for recycling or biomass use can be extremely challenging.

Challenge 2-2: Complex policy instruments

A second complexity challenge concerns the high number of policy instruments that are required and available to implement a CBBE. Quotas for plastic packaging recycling or for using recycled materials in the automobile sector, eco-design standards to facilitate re-use and recycling of products and obligations for packaging producers to collect waste are only the most prominent examples. Almost all legislation on forests, agriculture and waste and many more regarding industry, energy etc. affect the shape of the CBBE. While a wide range of policy options implies that there are many ways to move forward, it also makes it challenging to select the best options and to ensure policy consistency. Adding more and more policies can easily create conflicts (policy inconsistencies or messes) and increase administrative costs for businesses and governments (Braathen 2007; Rosenow et al. 2016).

Challenge 2-3: Unintended side-effects

The above example of excessive recycling illustrates that complex policy agendas face risks in the form of counterproductive effects. Next to excessive recycling that exacerbates resource depletion and pollution, there are other examples of such risks in the context of the CBBE:

- **Subsidy trap:** Supporting the transition with subsidies for sustainable products may actually accelerate resource depletion. Generally, subsidies tend to increase total resource consumption, whereas taxes or tradable permits tend to decrease resource use (Baumol and Oates 2005). This even applies to subsidies that are used to support sustainable products. For the circular economy, Hoogmartens et al. (2018) have demonstrated that promoting recycling with the help of subsidies leads to inefficiently high resource use. This is because subsidies, e.g. for secondary materials, incentivise a faster disposal of used goods and provide additional income that can be spent on additional products.
- **Biomass paradox:** As already mentioned, using biomass at some point will increase greenhouse gas emissions instead of reducing them. This is not only a challenge for energy uses of biomass but also for material uses, even for durable products such as construction materials (e.g., Hurmekoski et al. 2023). One reason is that biomass harvests usually do not allow for a complete transfer of carbon into products, but typically go along with substantial shares of low-quality residues and wastes that lead to a fast release of carbon to the atmosphere. Such counterproductive effects are closely related to the paradox of accounting for biogenic carbon emissions: While it can be reasonable to treat biomass as carbon neutral for certain *monitoring purposes* or in *product comparisons*, a zero-rating of emissions from biomass in *climate policies* is very likely to result in inefficient biomass use and higher than optimal GHG emissions (Lundgren 2008; Lintunen/Uusivuori 2016).
- **Circularity rebound:** Not only recycling and using biomass are prone to unwanted side effects. Even supposedly no-regret measures, such as reusing products, have to be approached with care. Creating or supporting existing second-hand markets can give people broader access to products that were previously unaffordable to them (Zink and Geyer 2017). This can be desirable from a social point of view, but such rebound effects also potentially undermine CBBE goals such as decoupling economic growth from resource use or reducing import dependencies.

This does not mean that subsidies, biomass or re-use should be entirely avoided. However, the examples show that policymakers have to apply respective policies with care. Ignoring such contradictions can compromise the effectiveness of policies and substantially increase the costs of the transition or environmental damages.

Challenge 2-4: Trade-offs

Another challenge for policymakers is that implementing policy measures that improve the EU's performance in regard to one goal may come at the expense of other goals (trade-offs). For example, improving the EU's global competitiveness requires competitive product prices, but low prices also tend to increase resource consumption (a potential trade-off between competitiveness and sustainable resource use). Many other examples can be found, such as increasing dependency on rare earths that are used for climate change mitigation technologies (supply security vs. climate change mitigation), decreasing availability of land for food production, when it is used for biomass production (food security vs. climate change mitigation) or increased labour intensity in an economy that expands repairing and recycling activities (job creation vs. competitiveness). Typically, such trade-offs cannot be solved entirely. Rather, the policy challenge is to be aware of them and to develop policy strategies that minimise such conflicts.

Challenge 2-5: Vagueness

Many CBBE goals and premises are still highly vague. For example, it is unclear whether the premise of decoupling resource use from economic growth refers to an absolute or a relative reduction of natural resource use. Similar ambiguities about the future CBBE concern

- the question of substitutability: E.g., is reducing resource consumption by limiting working time and thus possibly income justified by corresponding increases in environmental quality and leisure?, and
- the definition of “resource efficiency”: E.g., does this term include natural resources only or also labour? The latter option would limit increases of natural resource use efficiency with the help of - excessive - labour use.

These open questions are related to the fundamental question of weak vs. strong sustainability (Ayres et al. 2001; Neumayer 2013). Avoiding these questions substantially blurs the contours of the future CBBE. The resulting vagueness makes it difficult for policymakers to define clear targets. For businesses, it increases the challenge to anticipate future market conditions and to invest in the transition, e.g., in labour-intensive waste management or repair facilities.

Challenge 2-6: Resistance/lack of acceptance

Many policies lead to a redistribution of income or wealth, thereby triggering resistance against change. The CBBE transition will be no exception, but given its large scope and depth, extraordinary efforts may be required to secure public and industry acceptance. This challenge is aggravated by the fact that several benefits of the transition are intangible and do not always translate into obvious benefits, e.g., improved biodiversity in remote areas or benefits for future generations. Therefore, even if the CBBE transition results in higher sustainability, accompanying measures might be necessary to mediate possible negative effects in the short term and secure acceptance.

This subsection can be summarised into the following policy recommendation:

Policy recommendation 2: The CBBE transition has to be embedded into a clear strategic framework. This framework should specify key characteristics of the future CBBE, such as the desired degree of decoupling. It should also acknowledge unintended side-effects, trade-offs and social challenges, and provide clear answers on how to address these effects (ensure policy consistency and

reliability). Current strategic documents, such as the EU Circular Economy Action Plan or the EU Bioeconomy Strategy, do not sufficiently address these challenges.

The challenges from both tiers - markets and policy - underline that a careful and systematic reflection of the transition process and available policy options is needed for implementing a sustainable CBBE. The next section briefly outlines how these challenges have been addressed in SUSTRACK, before presenting the final policy recommendations.

2. METHODS: HOW TO DEAL WITH THE CHALLENGES

This section briefly describes how SUSTRACK has addressed the various barriers and challenges associated with creating a CBBE. Detailed accounts of the methods used can be found in previous SUSTRACK deliverables. Table 1 provides an overview to illustrate the premises under which the policy recommendations have been derived. This ensures transparency on normative foundations and limitations. While other ways to approach the transition may be equally valid, the selected options may provide an exemplary guide for policymakers on how to create effective and consistent CBBE policies.

Table 1: SUSTRACK approach to key challenges of the CBBE transition

Challenge	SUSTRACK approach
1-1 Lack of competitiveness	<p>As outlined in the barriers section, subsidising circular and bio-based products can cause counterproductive effects. Heavily relying on this instrument type also easily risks overstraining public budgets. Increasing the competitiveness of sustainable solutions should therefore be addressed mainly with other instruments such as taxes (for non-sustainable solutions), tradable permits or standards (e.g., quotas). For example, instead of subsidising recycled products, taxing virgin raw materials can improve market conditions for recycling.</p> <p>However, it is important to note that such a policy approach may lead to higher product prices, thereby creating a conflict with the EU goal of strengthening global competitiveness. It can also be problematic for low-income groups. One key solution to this dilemma between sustainability and competitiveness is innovation. More efficient technologies tend to decrease both resource intensity and prices of products, thus improving sustainability and global competitiveness. Therefore, innovation support policies take a leading role in addressing competitiveness in SUSTRACK. Another complementary policy strategy to improve competitiveness without undermining other goals is revenue recycling, e.g., from taxes, which is addressed below (barrier 2-6: resistance).</p>
1-2 Information barriers	<p>Lack of information can be addressed via information instruments such as labelling. The barrier description has revealed that too much (complex) or false information are further problems, possibly weakening the effectiveness of providing more information. Generally, considering the complexity of the required information, the administrative costs of information collection and provision, and the existence of various other market failures, the effectiveness and acceptance of information instruments may be limited. Because of that, SUSTRACK does not consider information barriers but focuses on “hard and binding” policies such as quotas for taxes. Policies recommended by SUSTRACK, therefore, possibly have to be complemented with additional information policies.</p>
1-3 Lock-in effects	<p>Inertia caused by physical infrastructures or social norms, customs and habits certainly justify political attention. To deal with the complexity of the transition, SUSTRACK focuses on a specific type of lock-in effect,</p>

Challenge	SUSTRACK approach
	<p>which is the difficulty for novel products to enter existing markets. Many novel products exhibit low-cost competitiveness because of their limited production volumes. Under such conditions, they are unable to exploit scale effects. In SUSTRACK, this challenge is addressed via the conceptual framing of innovation policies: These are not, in this report, restricted to research and development, but also include measures to improve the market penetration of novel products (similar to feed-in tariffs that are used to scale up renewable energy technologies, see Fischer et al. 2017; Marschinski and Quirion 2014). It is important to note that such anti-lock-in policies should be limited to novel products. As mentioned above, supporting also established sustainable products carries a high risk of unintended side effects.</p>
<p>1-4 Lack of technology</p>	<p>This barrier should be addressed via dedicated innovation measures, such as R&D subsidies or increased public research. These measures are essential for resolving many trade-offs of the CBBE transition, and therefore play a key role in SUSTRACK policy recommendations (see above:1-1 lack of competitiveness).</p>
<p>2-1 Complexity: policy targets</p>	<p>Achieving optimal recycling targets or sustainable levels of biomass use are “wicked problems”, i.e., associated with high uncertainties and side effects (Batie 2008). While wicked problems cannot, by definition, be solved easily, some policy approaches are more suited to dealing with them than others. This is reflected in the double-track approach of SUSTRACK:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For each sector, first, a market-based policy approach is considered. This approach focuses on correcting market failures that undermine a CBBE. This market correction modifies prices in a way that makes them reflect positive contributions of circular and bio-based products to the environment, thus improving their competitiveness. In such modified markets, (cost-)efficient recycling and biomass uses emerge in a decentralised way, without governments having to centrally prescribe targets (Baumol and Oates 2005). In other words, complexity is solved by using market mechanisms, similar to the general coordination of resource use in market economies via supply and demand. ● A second option to deal with complexity in the CBBE transition is a step-by-step approach (Purkus 2016) based on extensive policy evaluation and a constant update of policy instruments (until targets are achieved) and targets (until they optimally align with other CBBE targets). This strategy is reflected in the second SUSTRACK approach, which focuses on direct regulation (e.g., quotas, bans, sustainability criteria). <p>Both regulatory strategies present ideal types and are likely to be realized in a mixed form in real world politics. For example, a market-based policy approach can also entail stepwise trial and error processes (Baumol and Oates 1971). Both strategies - correction of market prices v.s. step-by-</p>

Challenge	SUSTRACK approach
	<p>step approach - can apply to both instrument types (market-based vs. direct regulation). In SUSTRACK, both strategies are discussed in the form of market-based vs. direct regulation policy approaches. This helps to isolate the strengths and weaknesses of each approach and policy instrument type in order to provide a transparent decision basis for policymakers.</p>
<p>2-2 Complexity: policy instruments</p>	<p>To deal with the large number of existing and suggested policy instruments, SUSTRACK made the following arrangements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● First, the project concentrates on “hard and binding” policies. This includes market-based policies such as taxes, tradable permits or subsidies and direct regulation such as quotas, bans, sustainability criteria. With some exceptions, SUSTRACK does not consider are information, nudging or voluntary instruments. SUSTRACK also does not discuss legally non-binding meta-policies such as strategies. Documents such as the EU Circular Economy Action Plan or the EU Biodiversity Strategy are taken into account as a given (static) policy environment - mainly in terms of policy goals and premises. ● Second, from the available policy instruments that were identified in literature reviews and with stakeholders (existing and proposed), SUSTRACK selected archetypical options according to specific policy functions that have to be fulfilled during the CBBE transition. This means that the selected instruments could be exchanged with other instruments that fulfil the same function. For example, in places where a carbon tax is discussed, an emissions trading system could be an equally valid solution, as both fulfil the same function of putting a price on carbon. The selected policies are documented in Annex I. Further details are provided in D5.3. ● Third, policy instruments were separated according to whether they address circularity or the bioeconomy. While overlaps between both concepts exist and the bioeconomy could be considered as a part of the overall circularity transition, both concepts constitute distinct policy challenges because they tend to focus on different types of resources (non-renewable vs. renewable). Each of these resource types is affected by specific market failures that require customized policy answers. For example, a sustainable use of biomass is challenged by the tendency of markets to neglect positive climate contributions of biomass in terms of removing carbon from the atmosphere (positive climate externalities, see, for example, Lintunen / Uusivuori 2016). This market failure does not apply to recycling batteries or reusing mineral-based construction materials. Another example is that regulating non-renewable resources has to deal with the question of how to sustainably (or efficiently) use finite natural resource stocks (e.g., Krautkramer 2005), whereas biomass is a

Challenge	SUSTRACK approach
	<p>renewable resource that requires policies that take into account the renewability of this resource (Baumol and Oates 2005).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fourth, the analysis in SUSTRACK has been limited to material uses of natural resources, thereby excluding all (bio-)energy-related policies. This decision was taken to avoid repetition in a policy field that is already at a high level of development in the EU.
<p>2-3 Unintended side-effects</p>	<p>To minimize unintended side-effects of CBBE policies - i.e. effects that contribute to increasing and inefficient resource use - SUSTRACK made the following arrangements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SUSTRACK has modelled the effects of the CBBE transition on GDP growth, employment and biomass use. This way, problematic impacts on these key variables could be identified and were considered in policy recommendations (see chapter 4). • In most cases, subsidies play a limited role in SUSTRACK except for innovation subsidies. In cases where general subsidies (i.e., including for non-innovative products) are suggested, this is motivated by increasing acceptance of the transition rather than by improving the competitiveness of sustainable products. Where such subsidies are applied, complementary policies seeking to limit total resource use probably must be more ambitious to mitigate unwanted side-effects of product subsidies. • To avoid unsustainable and inefficient use of biomass and also circularity rebound effects, each policy approach includes measures that curb total resource use.
<p>2-4 Trade-offs</p>	<p>To minimise trade-offs between different CBBE targets, SUSTRACK made the following arrangements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For each sector, a market-based policy approach is outlined that focuses on correcting market failures. This contributes to more efficient resource use. Efficiency implies (by definition) that trade-offs are minimised, at least those related to resource use. For example, an efficient recycling rate implies that recycling does not consume more resources (including pollution sinks) than it saves (e.g., Kinnaman et al. 2014). • Each policy approach includes innovation support policies for sustainable solutions. Sustainability innovations are a no-regret measure that can contribute to all CBBE goals, thus promoting change without creating trade-offs. For example, an innovative production technology can simultaneously reduce natural resource inputs (goal: sustainable resource management), respective GHG emissions from resource extraction, processing and consumption

Challenge	SUSTRACK approach
	(goal: climate protection), import dependency (goal: supply security) and product prices (goal: competitiveness).
2-5 Vagueness	As outlined above, policy makers do not necessarily have to specify each characteristic of the CBBE transition. Still, some fundamental features have to be determined by democratically legitimised policymakers, such as the question of which level of decoupling is desired (absolute vs. relative). In SUSTRACK, policy solutions are created in a way that allows adjusting them to different political CBBE visions (e.g., more or less ambitious transition). For example, where a resource tax is suggested, no tax level is specified. Thus, it is open to policymakers to choose a level that is consistent either with a CBBE leading to relative decoupling or a CBBE leading to absolute decoupling.
2-6 Resistance/lack of acceptance	To improve acceptance of CBBE policy approaches, each SUSTRACK approach features a subsidy, usually for innovations. These subsidies can be used to decrease financial burdens for businesses and, indirectly, consumers, by channelling revenues from taxes or tradable permits back to the private sector. Research on climate policies suggests that this can improve the acceptance of such measures at low costs (Kalkuhl et al. 2013; Bertram et al. 2015). Other options that are not covered by SUSTRACK could complement this strategy, e.g., the establishment of a Social CBBE Fund similar to the EU’s Social Climate Fund.

3. SOLUTIONS: WHAT ARE THE KEY POLICY OPTIONS

3.1 Which decisions do policymakers face?

Creating policies for the CBBE transition requires two decisions: First, policymakers have to choose the preferred policy *type*. Second, they have to select suited policy *instruments* (Figure 1).

Regarding policy *type*, SUSTRACK considers two types: direct regulation (quotas, bans, sustainability criteria etc.) and market-based instruments (taxes, tradable permits, subsidies etc.).

After choosing the preferred policy type, specific policy *instruments* must be selected and integrated into a consistent policy mix, i.e., a combination of several policy instruments. SUSTRACK made this selection according to policy functions that were deducted from key market failures that hinder the CBBE transition (for details, see D5.3).

Figure 1. Levels of policy choices

Typically, policy mixes can (and often do) include instruments of different types. However, even then, one policy instrument will typically be the dominant driver for change - again requiring policy makers to make a choice regarding the (leading) type. For example, in EU climate policies, the EU has decided to combine market-based policies (EU-ETS) with direct regulations (e.g., vehicle emission standards). In the transport sector, ETS allowance prices are not sufficient to initiate substantial emission reductions - therefore, emission reductions are mainly driven by emission standards and other policy instruments that take the leading role in the sector (see, for example, DEHSt 2025).

In SUSTRACK, both policy choices were analysed. The choice of which policy *type* should be preferred was approached by identifying strengths and weaknesses related to the instruments from each type (literature review and stakeholder discussions). The prioritisation of policy *instruments* has been facilitated with the help of stakeholders (for details, see D5.3 and D5.4).

3.2 Which policy approach should be used?

Stakeholders showed mixed preferences on policy approaches in all sectors of interest (textiles, chemicals, plastics, construction). On the one hand, they tend to prefer direct regulation, such as bans and standards (eco-design and sustainability criteria). On the other hand, they are worried that standards such as product criteria increase bureaucracy and associated costs. In regard to market-based instruments, a majority of stakeholders prefers subsidies but opposes the use of taxes. One reason for this result might be the high number of stakeholders from businesses engaged in SUSTRACK events, possibly resulting in a bias in favour of policies that shift transition costs to governments and society (tax payers). Some further inconsistencies can be found, for example, regarding the plastics sector: A high number of votes was given for applying eco-design criteria, but at the same time, the use of sustainability criteria (for material uses of biomass) was mostly rejected. Again, this could be explained by the mentioned stakeholder bias: Eco-design criteria for plastic products can be expected to improve market chances for suppliers of circular bio-based products. Sustainability criteria for biomass, on the other hand, imply higher feedstock costs and bureaucracy for these companies, thus limiting their competitiveness.

3.2.1 Direct regulation

Looking past cost-related stakeholder preferences, conclusions can be derived from the discussions on the strengths and weaknesses of each policy approach. Direct regulation received mixed comments in terms of **effectiveness** and, as already mentioned, invokes substantial concerns about excessive bureaucracy. For example, the effectiveness of applying quotas for using recycled fibres in the textile sectors was questioned because of a lack of supply of such fibres and related technology. In the chemicals sector, the effectiveness of thresholds for substances that inhibit the reuse or recycling of products was questioned in the light of market dynamics (a high number of new chemicals entering the market each year). It was assumed that such standards could be easily circumvented. A similar related concern was mentioned in regard to leakage effects, for example, if quotas or eco-design criteria apply to domestic producers only.

As for **bureaucracy**, implementing rules for cascading use of resources in sectors like plastics and construction could prove very challenging. Optimal cascading depends, among other things, on the possibility of recycling side streams or waste, to make the resources available for further material use. But, as the sustainability (and efficiency) of recycling itself is highly context-specific, complex cascading rules will be necessary to reflect different context conditions, possibly resulting in increased bureaucracy. If, on the other hand, simplified cascading rules are applied that neglect context specificity, cascading is likely to happen in places where it is very costly or to be avoided where it would be efficient (e.g., Schindler et al., 2024).

Stakeholders also highlighted the **limited flexibility** of direct regulation: For example, banning certain products from EU markets - similar to existing EU bans on selected single-use plastics - can be perceived by some consumers as a disproportionate measure if no sustainable alternatives are available. A market-based policy approach that relies on modifying prices would provide higher flexibility, because consumers would still have the option to buy these products, even though at higher costs (reflecting increased environmental impacts).

An additional feature of direct regulation that should be noted is that it possibly implies lower costs for businesses and consumers, and therefore higher **acceptance**. The above-mentioned stakeholder preference for direct regulation reflects that alternatives such as taxes or tradable permits often impose higher costs on producers and consumers (because tax payments or buying permits imply a transfer of financial resources from the private sector to governments). At first

glance, this can increase acceptance of such policies for the CBBE. However, direct regulation is often costlier (less efficient) for society as a whole, because it tends to disregard cost-saving potentials from varying cost structures in markets. For example, Cludius et al. (2019) have estimated that the EU-ETS has reduced climate change mitigation costs by up to 47 % in its second trading phase compared to the use of emissions standards. This is because permits trading accounts for the varying abatement costs of firms and shifts abatement efforts from high-cost to low-cost places (Baumol and Oates 2005). In consequence, while emission standards might have saved firms (and, indirectly, consumers) the costs of buying ETS allowances, this direct regulation approach would have substantially increased total abatement costs. This would have resulted in higher costs for a share of companies and higher prices for consumer goods produced by these companies in the long run. As these cost increases affect only some companies and possibly only certain segments of consumers, such costly policies might paradoxically face higher acceptance than market-based instruments. This paradox might be circumvented by redistributing revenues from market-based instruments back to producers or consumers, though.

Regarding **fairness**, direct regulation can have various effects. A feature that should be noted here is that direct regulation, such as bans or quotas, tends to affect people with different socioeconomic backgrounds in a similar way. For example, banning single-use plastics from EU markets affects poor and wealthy people alike. If, instead, taxes are used to limit the use of single-use plastics, this can lead to a situation where only high-income groups continue to consume the product while low-income groups are effectively excluded. Insofar as direct regulation increases the total costs of the CBBE transition (see previous paragraph), another fairness-related effect is that it possibly slows down economic growth and, subsequently, tax revenues that finance social policies. Thus, this type of regulation can indirectly increase social inequalities or require a shift to different (less budget-intensive) welfare measures.

These implications can be summarised in the following policy recommendation:

Policy recommendation 3: When using direct regulation such as quotas, bans or sustainability criteria, policy makers should

- *explore options to limit bureaucratic burdens, e.g., by providing standard values for certain sustainability assessments (similar to standard values in the EU RED for GHG emissions from bioenergy),*
- *complement quotas, bans, etc., with innovation support to ensure that sufficient sustainable options are available for complying with a quota or to mitigate the negative effects of a ban,*
- *limit their use to areas where no substantial efficiency losses are to be expected from their application and*
- *apply them in cases where market-based solutions would intensify social disparities and thus undermine acceptance of the CBBE transition.*

3.2.2 Market-based instruments

Regarding market-based policy options, stakeholders voiced fewer concerns but also fewer advantages. One possible reason is that they are less familiar with this type of policy intervention.

This could be a result of direct regulation currently dominating CBBE policies (e.g., extended producer responsibilities, recycling-related quotas or sustainability criteria for biomass uses in the energy sector).

Many comments concerned the **effectiveness** of market-based instruments: While generally a high effectiveness was assumed, some limitations were mentioned. In regard to a carbon price for fossil carbon and carbon from low-value biomass uses, leakage risks were mentioned. Such a price could lead to higher imports of (carbon-intensive) products from countries where no similar measures are in place. As outlined above, similar concerns were also raised in regard to direct regulation measures, though. As for innovation subsidies, their effectiveness was put into question because of the high share of SMEs in CBBE-related markets and their limited capacities to participate in bureaucratic funding procedures.

There were also some concerns about rising **bureaucracy** in relation to using market-based instruments. These concerns were related to pollution taxes that could be used to internalise environmental externalities from chemicals. A tax on fossil carbon did not raise similar concerns, possibly because stakeholders mostly belonged to CBBE-related businesses. Another possible reason is that the carbon taxation was suggested in the form of an upstream tax, thus avoiding costly assessments at the (final) product level. These examples illustrate that administrative burdens depend on the specific instrument and its design. High bureaucracy may also be associated with a tax on ‘fast fashion’ or on ‘low-value biomass uses’. In both cases, it might be difficult to decide what is included in these categories and what is not, possibly leading to complex and elaborate assessment criteria. Applying direct regulation instruments such as bans or product standards may face similar challenges, though. In regard to biomass, a (relatively) simple solution could be to include *all* emissions from biomass into carbon pricing, at least for forest biomass, as this contributes to a cost-efficient balance of using wood for carbon storage (forests, harvested wood products) and for bioenergy (van Kooten et al. 1995; Lundgren 2008; Lintunen and Uusivuori 2016). It also supports efficient wood cascading without having to rely on complex cascading rules (Miettinen and Ollikainen 2024; Schindler et al. 2024). However, including a renewable resource into carbon pricing is counterintuitive for many and will therefore most likely raise questions of acceptance.

Acceptance generally has to be considered by policymakers when using market-based policies. The distributional effects of instruments such as taxes are complex and cannot be outlined in detail here (see, for example, Fullerton 2011). Some important effects include the transfer of financial means from the private sector to governments. This can be mitigated by various means, such as by ‘grandfathering’ permits or channelling revenues back to companies or consumers via innovation subsidies or tax reliefs. Respective measures should be planned carefully, though, to avoid distortive effects.

These considerations can be summarised in the following policy recommendation related to using market-based instruments in the CBBE transition:

Policy recommendation 4: When using market-based instruments such as taxes, tradable permits or subsidies, policy makers should

- a. complement taxes and tradable permits with measures that minimise leakage effects, such as carbon border adjustments,***
- b. design innovation subsidies in a way that limits administrative burden for SMEs,***

- c. use, if possible, downstream instead of upstream taxes and*
- d. recycle revenues back to businesses and consumers to improve acceptance.*

Some stakeholders reflected on the current reluctance to employ market-based policies for the CBBE transition and recommended making greater use of such instruments. This again illustrates the fundamental dilemma faced by companies: While they are worried about cost increases for their business models from market-based policies, they are also aware of the often-higher bureaucratic challenges associated with elaborate direct regulations. Policy makers should therefore reflect more systematically, whether direct regulation is suitable to be the leading policy type to manage a process as complex as the CBBE transition. Already today, bureaucracy is a major barrier for economic development and competitiveness in the EU (European Commission 2025). It should be questioned, therefore, whether a CBBE is likely to thrive within a complex web of detailed quotas, sustainability criteria for products and feedstocks or similar interventionist rules.

A possible rule of thumb is to use direct regulation as a back-up option in contexts where market-based solutions are inadequate. Especially the chemicals and the plastics sectors could require (some) direct regulation. Many chemicals are too hazardous to be regulated via volatile, price-based instruments, and changing the feedstock base in plastics production possibly requires carbon prices at a level that may be politically difficult to establish (Zibunas et al. 2022).

Policy recommendation 5: To address the trade-off between acceptance by businesses (production costs) and bureaucracy (transaction costs), policymakers should carefully assess when to use market-based policies and when direct regulation is favourable or a useful addition. Potentials of market-based policies to limit administrative costs should be identified and exploited to make the CBBE transition less bureaucratic.

3.3 Which policy instruments should be used?

SUSTRACK has identified possible sets of policy instruments to accelerate the CBBE transition in each of the analysed sectors (textiles, plastics, chemicals, construction - see Annex I and D5.3). For each sector, they include instruments to increase supply and demand for more sustainable products, as well as instruments to limit resource use for sustainability and efficiency reasons.

A survey and various stakeholder workshops did not yield consistent preferences for or against individual policy instruments. The results vary depending on the method applied (survey vs. prioritisation in workshops) and across participating countries. Regarding different national backgrounds, qualitative discussions on challenges and opportunities of individual EU member states did not explain the respective preferences. Again, it might be possible that for many stakeholders it is difficult to assess the manifold transition challenges and relate them to the manifold strengths and weaknesses of individual policy instruments.

A second point to consider is that the suggested exemplary policy instruments in SUSTRACK were identified with the help of literature and earlier stakeholder events. These proposals are rarely

the result of a systematic process of comparing different instruments with each other. Rather, they appear to reflect individual preferences for or familiarity with different policy interventions. Hence, SUSTRACK has focused on *policy functions* that should be fulfilled in the CBBE transition (support the transition, and limit resource use). The suggested policy instruments should therefore be read as exemplary options that could be replaced by other policy instruments with similar functions. For example, a tax could be replaced in many instances by tradable permits with basically similar effects in terms of efficiency and effectiveness (for similarities and differences see, e.g., Haites 2018).

Still, based on the above considerations, some conclusions on individual policy solutions can be derived:

- **Support for innovative solutions** should play a key role in the transition. This policy option received favourable ratings from many stakeholders and is a no-regret measure that helps to reduce trade-offs, for example, between competitiveness and environmental goals (see chapter 1). It is important to keep in mind that the term innovation here includes not only research and development, which is already covered by many research programs such as EU Horizon, but also the process of market penetration. Thus, similar to feed-in-tariffs for renewable energies, it can be reasonable (efficient and effective) in some cases to establish financial support measures for key CBBE products to scale up their production volumes (exploitation of scale effects). Whether this support takes the form of tax reductions, loan guarantees, direct payments, quotas for innovative solutions, or other means is a secondary question.
- **Sustainability criteria** for material uses of biomass should be applied when the transition is steered via quotas, product subsidies or similar instruments that tend to increase biomass demand. Even though material uses are often superior to energy uses regarding climate change mitigation, they can still conflict with this and other CBBE goals (e.g., food security) (regarding climate change, see, for example, Hurmekoski et al. 2023; Philippidis et al. 2023).
- **Quotas for non-fossil feedstocks** can be a reasonable option to trigger change in sectors where transition costs are too high for market-based instruments to be effective. Similar to renewable energy quotas that complement carbon pricing in the transport sector, such quotas could be applied to the sectors plastics and chemicals. Here, costs for using recycled materials or sustainable biomass are (currently) so high that carbon prices of several hundred Euros per ton CO_{2e} might be necessary to induce changes in the feedstock base (Zibunas et al. 2022).
- **Carbon pricing** for fossil feedstocks and low-value biomass uses can still be a way in some sectors to improve the competitiveness of sustainable feedstocks, possibly with low administrative efforts if applied upstream (suppliers of fossil feedstocks for material uses). As outlined in D5.3, including the waste sector in the EU-ETS is unlikely to be effective, though. Lump sum waste fees often distort the price signal, thus providing little incentives for consumers and producers to switch to less carbon-intensive alternatives. Therefore, other ways of carbon pricing have to be found. Despite being counterintuitive for many, it is important to subject biomass to carbon pricing as well, at least low-value uses of forest biomass such as forest bioenergy or single-use products made of wood. Otherwise, even with biomass sustainability criteria, there is a high risk of undermining carbon storage in the land use sector and wood cascading (Lintunen and Uusivuori 2016; Schindler et al. 2024).

Policy recommendation 6: Regarding individual policy solutions, innovation support, sustainability criteria for material biomass uses and quotas for non-fossil feedstocks are plausible options to accelerate the transition. In a market-based policy setting, carbon pricing can be an alternative to quotas and sustainability criteria. In the sectors plastics and chemicals, quotas are possibly more suitable instruments, while carbon pricing may be more effective and efficient in sectors such as textiles and construction.

4. CUSTOMISATION: HOW TO CONSIDER THE INDIVIDUAL NEEDS OF MEMBER STATES?

Many policy solutions do not only need to be customised to certain economic sectors, but also to country-specificities (e.g., legal, political, cultural, etc.). SUSTRACK therefore organised workshops in several EU countries to assess whether the suggested policy instruments would be applicable in the respective national contexts, and to identify barriers and opportunities that require policy adjustments (see D5.4). While there were varying preferences between countries regarding policy instruments, no major concerns regarding country-specific barriers or opportunities have been raised. This indicates that the instruments suggested in the literature and by stakeholders do not face substantial legal, political or other obstacles, at least not in the more general form they were discussed. This finding is also consistent with the fact that many instruments of such types already exist at the EU level or in these countries (e.g., recycling quotas, carbon price or biomass sustainability criteria).

A need to customise policies to individual EU member states could also arise from differences in the transition performance. For example, countries where waste management infrastructure is lacking might find it challenging to comply with ambitious EU quotas for using recycled materials. In this regard, the SUSTRACK monitoring approach for the CBBE transition (see D2.4) provides the background to identify possible country-specific policy needs in three dimensions: Sustainable management of resources, environmental performance and economic relevance of the CBBE (numbers and figures in this section are based on the SUSTRACK monitor: <https://sustrack.eu/monitoring-system>; see also D2.4).

In regard to sustainable resource management, the CBBE monitoring reveals large differences between countries that are just starting the transition process and countries that are more advanced already (Figure 2). This variable considers various indicators, such as the use of recycled or reused material, recycling rates of municipal waste, recovery of biowaste and the bio-based share of consumption goods. In emerging CBBE countries, for example, on average only 16 % of municipal waste is recycled, while in more advanced CBBE countries the average recycling rate is 56 %.

Policies that pose uniform restrictions on all member states regarding waste management can therefore easily overwhelm some countries or squander potential within others. It can, therefore, be reasonable to differentiate policies such as quotas for recycling or for using recycled materials, at least temporarily. Another implication could be that less advanced CBBE countries require additional financial support or other forms of assistance.

An interesting question in this regard is whether uniform progress regarding the CBBE transition is desirable in all EU member states. Considering that countries tend to specialise in different economic activities, it can be reasonable for some countries to focus on recycling activities, while other countries specialise in utilising the recycled materials. For example, for countries with no relevant textile industry, it could be disproportionate to acquire costly technologies for processing used fibres for limited production volumes. Such stark variations in the CBBE transition process could therefore also be an argument for using market-based policies that provide more flexibility for individual countries or industrial actors. Taking the example of textile recycling, if taxes on (virgin) fossil feedstocks are applied, each country or company could weigh the costs and benefits of continued use of these fossil feedstocks at higher prices with existing technologies versus switching to recycled materials, including the costs for new technologies.

Bioeconomy Clusters in Europe

Resource management typology, 2022

Figure 2: Sustainable resource management performance in EU27 in 2022

Considering the **environmental performance**, this variable looked at the GHG emissions intensity of the bioeconomy, whether countries are on track to reach their climate targets for the land use sector (LULUCF) and how efficiently biomass is used in the economy (biomass use relative to GDP). For example, advanced countries in this respect show an average GHG emissions intensity of below 0,5 kg CO_{2e} per Euro generated in the bioeconomy, while emissions in the least advanced countries are in the range of 0,7 kg and higher (Figure 3).

Such differences between countries could imply that some need to step up their efforts to guarantee an ecologically safe transition. For EU policymakers, a conclusion could be that CBBE policies have to be supplemented with additional support (or restrictions) regarding environmental performance. For example, if a country is not on track regarding protecting and enhancing its forest carbon sinks, additional EU funding for forestry measures could be granted to strengthen this sink. Another implication could be to restrict financial support for the use of forest biomass for a certain period, in order to prevent further pressures on natural carbon sinks.

Bioeconomy Clusters in Europe

Environmental performance typology, 2022

Figure 3: Environmental performance of the bioeconomy in EU27

Variations in the economic performance of the bioeconomy could be a further point of discussion about customising EU CBBE policies. This indicator considers the contribution of a country's bioeconomy to total value creation (Gross Value Added, GVA), the contribution to employment and labour productivity (Figure 4). For example, the bioeconomy's share in total value addition ranges from 2 % in some countries to 12 % in others. It is challenging, though, to directly translate this into policy conclusions. For example, a large contribution of the CBBE to total value creation might reflect a large share of agriculture and forestry in an economy. However, advanced economies are often characterised by a declining share of this primary sector in favour of rising contributions from secondary (manufacturing) and tertiary (services) sectors. Hence, a small share of the bioeconomy's value addition might result from high economic development or other factors such as a lack of biomass resources due to geographical characteristics. Still, if differences persist even when such distorting influences are accounted for, they might provide a starting point for dedicated support measures for less advanced countries, e.g., in the form of improved knowledge and technology transfer to improve labour productivity.

Bioeconomy Clusters in Europe

Economic competitiveness performance typology, 2021

Figure 4: Economic performance of the bioeconomy

Policy recommendation 7: *The varying degree of progress in the EU member states can justify a customisation of policy measures, such as a variation of targets and quotas, additional support for waste management or restricted support for activities that potentially conflict with environmental targets. Different natural conditions or specializations in the global economy should be accounted for, though.*

5. STABILISATION: HOW TO ADDRESS SIDE-EFFECTS OF THE TRANSITION

A process that is as far-reaching as the CBBE transition is likely to affect macroeconomic variables such as economic growth and total employment. Negative impacts in this regard can require additional policy measures to support economic stability and acceptance. For this reason, SUSTRACK modelled the implications of the CBBE transition for both indicators (for details see D4.1 - D4.3). In addition to impacts on growth and employment, changes in biomass demand during the transition were assessed to quantify the need for policies to limit or redirect biomass demand in order to minimise trade-offs with goals such as climate change mitigation, biodiversity protection or food security.

The modelling assessed transition impacts in selected sectors in Germany (construction, plastics), Italy (textiles) and the Netherlands (chemicals). A business-as-usual scenario was compared with two scenarios of varying CBBE ambition levels (Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution). The model also considered effects from isolated national transitions vis-à-vis transitions that were embedded in a transformation of the entire EU. The general findings regarding impacts on economic growth, employment and biomass demand are largely consistent in all countries (sectors) and both transition scenarios.

5.1 Impacts on economic growth

In regard to GDP growth, both transition scenarios show higher growth in the long term (2050) compared to business as usual. However, in the plastics and textile industry, growth is stagnant or even negative in the medium term (until around 2040), indicating a challenging transition phase. It should be noted that this transition is accompanied by a substantial reduction in consumption volumes. This means that, in the long term, negative growth effects from reduced production are offset by positive growth effects from a more circular and bio-based production (decoupling). As the model considers domestic consumption only, it is also possible that total production - including for export - is stable or even rises. In this case, GDP growth could be even higher, but also material demand and GHG emissions. This could be beneficial or detrimental for global climate change mitigation, depending on the relative climate efficiency of domestic production in the EU compared to other regions.

The consumption of virgin raw materials declines substantially in all sectors, sometimes by more than 75 % (Bio-Revolution scenario for construction and textiles). This is a result of (assumed) increased recycling and reuse, but also from demographics (shrinking population). In combination with increased sectoral output growth, this implies not only relative but absolute decoupling (decreasing total material consumption despite economic growth).

For policymakers, the implications are that the transition can increase economic growth in the long run. However, in some sectors, negative growth rates are possible before economic benefits manifest. This can spur resistance from industry that may result in political conflicts about the competitiveness of national and EU economies. Counter-cyclical economic policy could mediate such conflicts, e.g., the provision of financial support for the sectors during challenging transition periods and increased taxation once the transition is advanced and the sectors have recovered and thrive.

These results should be interpreted with care because they rely on the assumption that bio-based and circular products generally result in higher added value than their fossil or linear counterparts. The underlying idea is that consumers appreciate the increased sustainability of respective products and thus have a higher willingness to pay for them. If this is not the case and consumers value only a product's function (instead of its altered resource base), less or even negative long term economic GDP growth may result from the transition.

It should be considered, however, that the model also shows a reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and other sources of environmental pollution. The related increases in welfare are not necessarily visible in GDP figures, as these do not comprehensively consider environmental goods (e.g., Kubiszewski et al. 2013). Generally, with the CBBE transition being motivated (also) by a more sustainable management of natural resources, progress in this regard may come in the form of less tangible benefits (better environmental quality), benefits that lie outside the EU (improved environmental quality resulting from decreased pollution due to lower resource extraction in a third country) or increased welfare of future generations.

To ensure enough tangible (visible) benefits within the EU and in the near term, it can therefore be important to put special attention on increasing the competitiveness of the domestic economies by supporting innovations. Alternatively, the visibility of CBBE benefits could be improved by replacing (or at least complementing) the narrow GDP indicator with more comprehensive measures of welfare, such as ISEW, GPI, HDI, IWI or others (e.g., Costanza et al. 2014). This could help to raise awareness for intangible benefits of the CBBE transition and thereby increase acceptance.

Another (complementary) policy strategy could be to emphasise the increased sustainability of EU production via marketing tools to gain a competitive advantage in global markets. This obviously depends on the willingness to pay for sustainable products in countries outside the EU, but could also contribute to encouraging other global regions to make their economies more sustainable.

Policy recommendation 8: Effects of the CBBE transition on economic growth should be monitored closely. Negative impacts may require macroeconomic policy strategies such as temporary increases in public spending. Intensified innovation support, broader measures of welfare and strategic marketing efforts can help to offset these impacts.

5.2 Increased demand for biomass

As for the use of biomass, the scenario results show an increased demand for land to cultivate biomass, despite decreasing material consumption and increasing recycling rates in each sector. Increased demand for bio-based raw materials can lead to higher harvest rates in forests and the loss of agricultural land for food and feed production. Studies such as Hurmekoski et al. 2023 and Philippidis et al. 2023 show that this can perpetuate or even increase total GHG emissions. Increases in emissions could result, for example, from a reduction in forest carbon sinks due to increased harvests. Because harvesting and processing wood typically lead to substantial amounts of byproducts and residues that are often used for energy production, GHG emissions can increase even if harvested (round-)wood is prioritised for material uses. This risk persists until CBBE innovations substantially increase the share of wood from harvests and waste that can be transformed into wood products ensuring long-term carbon storage similar to forests.

Next to the risk of undermining forest carbon sinks, an increased demand for agricultural biomass can conflict with food security or lead to GHG emissions from indirect land use changes (e.g., Merfort et al. 2021).

Increasing land use efficiency and optimising the use of marginal and degraded lands could be strategies to address the increased land demand in a sustainable manner. A recent study by Elbersen et al. (2025) indicates there is enough marginal land in the EU to meet the increased demand from the modelled scenarios (see D4.3). Still, many of these land areas are currently used despite being marginal. Such usages can include the provision of ecosystem services. Therefore, simply directing additional biomass demand from the CBBE transition towards these areas might conflict with adjacent policy targets such as biodiversity protection. A possible solution could be to identify priority areas among all land use types that currently provide low value for both nature and the economy. These might include marginal areas, but also other types of land use. Defining such areas could go along with reduced monitoring and certification requirements, if the designation of these areas already includes checking the compatibility of their use with environmental and other policy targets.

When defining such priority areas for additional biomass cultivation, it should be considered that future developments could reduce the availability of low-value land uses. For example, the EU Nature Restoration Law may require member states to decrease the use intensity of certain areas. To minimise costs (production losses from forests and agriculture), member states might select low-productive areas such as marginal land to meet Nature Restoration Law requirements, thus possibly excluding (intensified) biomass cultivation. Hence, there is possibly a trade-off between increased demand for biomass and environmental protection. Identifying land use options that provide synergies between both targets could be one strategy to mitigate this conflict (e.g., use of biomass that is harvested for nature conservation purposes).

Additional measures to ensure the sustainability of increasing biomass demand may be necessary. Such measures could include promoting vegetarian diets, because feed crops occupy more than half of EU agricultural land (Guyomard et al. 2021). Another option is to improve the efficiency of existing land use. For example, forest management intensity tends to be too high in the EU because climate externalities of wood use are not reflected in market prices (Lundgren 2008; Lintunen and Uusivuori 2016). Internalising these effects can contribute to more efficient land use and higher availability of biomass. To summarise, a CBBE transition can provide many benefits but comes along with possible trade-offs from increased demand for biomass. Identifying priority areas for additional biomass cultivation and improving land-use efficiency can mitigate associated risks.

Policy recommendation 9: To mitigate trade-offs related to the use of biomass (land area), increasing demand for this resource could be met by designating priority areas for additional biomass production. Such priority areas should be characterised by simultaneously low economic and ecological value or allow for win-win solutions regarding biomass production and the environment. In addition to this, potential to increase overall land use efficiency should be identified and exploited.

5.3 Shifting employment

Concerning transition effects on employment, scenario results consistently indicate that employment in the affected sectors declines, in the plastics sector even up to 50 % compared to current levels. As the analysed sectors constitute only a part of the countries' industrial sectors, these negative employment outcomes have only limited impacts on total industry employment in the model. However, if other industry sectors are also included in the CBBE transition, further, more serious effects on aggregate employment may arise. How the transition changes employment, therefore, strongly depends on the scope of the transition. This also applies to whether other countries undergo the transition into a CBBE. If the entire EU is transformed, model results show that total employment in the analysed sectors tends to increase, e.g., due to higher demand from other countries for sustainable products.

One implication for policymakers is therefore that the CBBE transition should be tackled not in isolation but in a coordinated manner at the EU level or, ideally, globally. Second, labour market policies may be necessary to cushion potential negative employment effects in individual sectors during the transition. As the model results show, decreasing deployment in transforming sectors may be offset by increasing deployment in other sectors. Still, this does not necessarily imply that everyone from the transforming sectors will easily find new employment, because other sectors often require different skills. Hence, retraining and re-education programs might be necessary to reduce such labour market frictions, i.e., help people find new jobs in other areas. Regarding these labour market effects, it should also be noted that the CBBE transition is a gradual and multi-layered process. It entails several different developments that possibly take place at different timelines. For example, switching the resource base to biomass and increasing recycling rates may happen at different speeds. This also implies that job losses or job creation do not take the form of shocks, but most likely occur in an incremental manner, giving people and industries time to adapt.

On a more general note, modern economic growth generally tends to shift employment from industry to the service sector, even though this effect has slowed down in advanced economies in the last decades (e.g., Kim 2020). The CBBE transition could accelerate this development or be considered part of it. It therefore underlines the need to adjust policy frames to this altered economic structure, i.e., strengthen labour rights in the service sector that is often associated with precarious working conditions and lower wages.

Policy recommendation 10: The CBBE transition should be targeted at the EU level to create markets that are large enough to support sustainable business models. To facilitate the transition in the labour market, targeted educational measures should be implemented that qualify people for positions in new industries or services. Standards regulating these new sectors should be reassessed in order to ensure equal or better income and working conditions.

6. ORIENTATION: WHERE TO START AND WHAT TO DO NEXT?

The previous sections and the policy solutions identified in SUSTRACK illustrate both the complexity of the policy task to shape a CBBE and the interconnectedness of its individual elements. For example, before a quota for using recycled materials is set, policymakers should provide a policy framework that ensures a sufficient supply of such materials (e.g., adequate waste management policies). Another example is putting measures to ensure the sustainability of biomass supply before targets or policy support to replace fossil fuels with bio-based feedstocks are established (e.g., sustainability criteria or carbon pricing of GHG emissions from biomass).

This chapter, therefore, outlines possible roadmaps for CBBE policies for the sectors textiles, chemicals, plastics and construction. These roadmaps are based on the following elements:

1. the policy options selected in previous steps of SUSTRACK (see Annex I and D5.3),
2. stakeholder preferences for the most urgent policy changes, identified in the SUSTRACK DEPLOY policy workshops (see D5.4) and
3. qualitative insights from the literature and stakeholder discussions about cross-connections between individual policy instruments, e.g., in the form of prerequisites or synergies (see D5.3).

These roadmaps should be considered as exemplary pathways and serve to illustrate possible sequences of legislative steps. Whether or not they constitute preferable policy pathways depends on how policymakers weigh the strengths and weaknesses associated with each instrument (see chapter 2).

6.1 Roadmap example: Textiles

Initiating change in the textile sector could start by expanding spending for research and development regarding sustainable solutions (e.g., recycling technologies for used clothing). While preferences from stakeholders belonging to this sector were mixed, there was a general preference of stakeholders from all sectors for financial support (subsidies), especially for innovative solutions. Increasing R&D support can generally be considered as a low- or no-regret option, as it supports other policy measures and comes with few trade-offs (see chapter 2). One important synergy is that innovations help to decrease the costs to comply with quotas for sustainable feedstocks or with pollution taxes, because innovations contribute to establishing sustainable alternatives and to decreasing their costs. In this sense, R&D subsidies are similar to feed-in-tariffs for renewable energy: While these policies have limited impact on GHG emissions reduction in the presence of an emissions cap (EU-ETS), they help to substantially reduce the costs of compliance with the EU-ETS (Fischer et al. 2017; Marschinski and Quirion 2014). Similarly, before restricting or pricing less sustainable business models in the textile (or any other) sector, the creation of affordable alternatives should be supported. R&D support should also be considered as an early policy step, because innovation often takes time before yielding results that can impact markets, while other policy measures induce change relatively fast. Of course, innovation can also be triggered (possibly even more efficiently in some cases) by other means, such as public research or quotas. While these are potentially valid alternatives (or complements) to R&D subsidies, the latter include the benefit of financial transfers to the private sector. These can help to improve acceptance of the transition. Furthermore, shifting the costs of innovation

entirely to the private sector (companies) by using quotas for innovative textiles comes with a risk of ineffectiveness or non-compliance. The market for advanced biofuels illustrates these risks: In Germany, the quota for advanced fuels mainly led to an increase in imports of resources from Asia, many with questionable sustainability characteristics.¹ Consequently, the quota did little to promote domestic innovation as originally intended. In the US, an initial quota for advanced biofuels had to be relaxed after fossil fuel suppliers initiated several lawsuits, arguing that they were not able to ensure a sufficient supply of such fuels (Powers 2016).

In addition to R&D support, stakeholders also consistently argued that substantial and direct support for sustainable solutions is required for them to become competitive. In the textile sector, a “green VAT” was proposed repeatedly, i.e., a reduced value-added tax rate for sustainable solutions such as second-hand textiles or products made of recycled fibres. Such broad financial support, however, risks circular economy rebound effects (Zink and Geyer 2017), i.e., increasing total demand for textiles. This could offset positive economic and ecological effects from supporting sustainable practices. To mitigate this risk, policies that curb resource use should be implemented prior to such tax cuts. There was no consistent voting in regard to what such policies should be. In our roadmap example, we choose (upstream) taxes on the use of fossil feedstocks in the textile industry and on ‘fast fashion’. Starting with such taxes before providing tax relief also has the advantage of generating revenues that can be used to finance the tax reduction. As a carbon tax rate should be low in the beginning and rise carefully in order to prevent market disruptions, introducing this tax before reducing another gives time to increase tax rates (or reduce emission allowance in the case of tradeable permits) for providing relevant revenues that help finance the VAT reduction.

While both taxes on fossil carbon and ‘fast fashion’ could, in theory, be implemented simultaneously, starting with the carbon tax may yield faster results. A ‘fast fashion’ tax is likely to pose some time-consuming design and implementation challenges before it can take effect. First, a definition of what constitutes ‘fast fashion’ would have to be created, which might not be trivial and trigger substantial rent seeking (lobbying). Second, as China and other Asian nations are major suppliers of textiles that are often considered ‘fast fashion’, taxing textiles for sustainability reasons may require strategies to prevent international trade conflicts. While measures directly addressing climate change may be seen as acceptable under WTO rules (GATT Art. XX) in times of carbon border adjustment policies (EU CBAM), taxing ‘fast fashion’ as a proxy measure for various environmental impacts could more easily be perceived as a disguised protectionist measure.² Table 2 presents an overview of the roadmap.

¹ <https://www.dlg.org/en/magazine/biodiesel-the-scam-with-hydrogenated-vegetable-oils>.

² See, for example, the current debate on the fast fashion tax proposal in France: <https://english.news.cn/20250326/b85c9b2a2d1f4347944217c38dbdef41/c.html>.

Table 2: Exemplary roadmap for the textile sector

Step	Policy instrument	Rationale for selection and order
1	R&D subsidies for innovative technologies or practices related to bio-based textiles and textile re-use or recycling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • decreases the costs of abatement measures triggered by a subsequent carbon tax (step 2) • high approval by stakeholders • no regret option • innovation takes time
2	Fossil carbon tax	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • balances rebound effects from “green VAT” (step 4) • provides revenues for “green VAT” (step 4)
3	“Fast fashion tax”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • balances rebound-effects related to biomass from “green VAT” (step 4) • possibly requires more time to design than the carbon tax (fast fashion definition/criteria, compatibility with WTO rules)
4	“Green VAT” - reduced value-added tax for second-hand textiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • supports market entry of novel solutions after their development based on R&D support (step 1) • complements carbon tax (step 2) that may have limited effects on fibre mixes with low shares of fossil fibres (e.g., fossil-based elastane) • short-term option to recycle revenues from taxation (steps 2+3) back to consumers to improve acceptance

6.2 Roadmap example: Chemicals

In the (non-plastics) chemical sector, change should again be initiated with targeted subsidies for research, development and market entry. With the Save and Sustainable by Design framework (SSbD), the EU has already established criteria for guiding such efforts. For the rationales of starting with this measure, see the previous roadmap on textiles.

Regarding sector-specific preferences, a quota for non-fossil feedstocks in chemicals production was ranked among the most urgent measures to boost circular and biobased chemicals during stakeholder consultations. This preference is in line with challenges associated with market-based alternatives to such a quota. For example, the effectiveness of carbon pricing in this sector may be limited due to very high abatement costs (Zibunas et al. 2022).

Before such a quota can be established, though, sustainability criteria for (material uses of) biomass should to be defined. Otherwise, the quota may trigger rising demand for biomass that conflicts with environmental policy targets such as the EU climate target in the land use sector

(LULUCF). Typically, sustainability conflicts are associated with using biomass for energy. However, biomass demand for material uses can equally undermine sustainability or increase climate mitigation costs (Jonsson et al. 2021; Schulte et al. 2022; Hurmekoski et al. 2023; Hu et al. 2025). Against this background, a supportive policy measure could be to reduce support for bioenergy, to reallocate more biomass from existing harvest levels to material uses. As mentioned in chapter 4, the designation of priority areas for additional biomass cultivation could also contribute to aligning quotas for sustainable feedstocks with sustainability, possibly at lower administrative costs (fewer criteria or reporting requirements).

To improve circularity, a final step could be to put a price on chemical pollution, e.g., in the form of a tax. This option was preferred by some stakeholders over thresholds for selected Substances of Concern (not: Substances of Very High Concern, SVHC), because thresholds were considered as being ineffective given the high market dynamics in the chemical sector (rapid succession of new chemicals). Still, pollution taxation faces several challenges on its own, which may result in a complicated and lengthy policymaking process. A key question in this regard is how to tax chemical substances when related environmental (or health) damages vary widely, depending on how they are used or disposed of and where they enter the environment (e.g., Tietenberg 1995; Grizzetti et al. 2016). Managing such non-point pollution sources is an example of so-called wicked problems that defy simple solutions (Batie 2008), despite decades of research (Slunge and Alpizar 2019). Another challenging question is how a homogeneous EU approach on taxing chemical pollution can be designed, given that in many EU countries pollution taxes already exist, albeit often for specific emission pathways or individual environmental media only (e.g., waste water levies or air pollution taxes). To avoid double taxation, the existence of such specific pricing instruments would have to be taken into account, at least if a general upstream taxation approach is chosen. These challenges indicate the magnitude of the task of limiting chemical pollution. Nevertheless, to improve circularity in the EU, policymakers must step up efforts in this regard, not only regarding Substances of Very High Concern, but also for many other chemicals that pose relevant barriers for circular practices (Johansson 2023). Table 3 provides an overview of the roadmap.

Table 3: Exemplary roadmap for the chemical sector

Step	Policy instrument	Rationale for selection and order
1	R&D subsidies for developing and scaling up low-risk, non-fossil-based chemicals and toxic-free products according to the EU SSbD framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● decreases the costs of abatement measures triggered by quota (step 3) ● high approval by stakeholders ● no regret option ● innovation takes time
2	Biomass sustainability criteria + designation of priority areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prerequisite for quota (step 3)
3	Quota for non-fossil feedstock shares in chemicals production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● stakeholder priority ● high effectiveness
4	Pollution tax	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● higher flexibility than pollution standards (thresholds/bans)

6.3 Roadmap example: Plastics (non-packaging)

Advancing circularity and feedstock change in non-packaging plastics should again start with financial support for innovative solutions, to decrease compliance costs with subsequent regulations (see textiles roadmap). According to stakeholders, eco-design criteria to facilitate recycling or other R-strategies and a quota for using recycled materials are essential steps to move forward. Eco-design criteria for major sources of plastic waste - such as currently under debate for cars³ - ideally predate quotas for using recycled materials, because they possibly contribute to the supply of secondary materials that facilitate compliance with such quotas.

Another stakeholder priority was carbon pricing for fossil feedstocks used in the plastics industry. This step could complement quotas or substitute them in cases where they are not feasible (e.g., because of a lack of adequate recycling materials or technologies to use these materials). In such instances, carbon taxes create incentives for respective innovations in addition to R&D subsidies.

Regarding biomass, subsidies for bio-based plastics have been ranked high by stakeholders as well. Such subsidies provide additional incentives for scaling up bio-based business models. This is likely to be necessary because carbon pricing alone may not suffice to trigger change (Aidt et al. 2017; Zibunas et al. 2022). To ensure sustainable biomass use, such subsidies should be coupled with sustainability criteria for material biomass uses or with a carbon price on low-value biomass uses (bioenergy, single-use plastics, etc.). This contributes to shifting biomass resources from low- to higher-value uses (e.g., Miettinen and Ollikainen 2024). Table 4 provides an overview of the roadmap.

Table 4: Exemplary roadmap for the plastics sector (non-packaging)

Step	Policy instrument	Rationale for selection and order
1a	R&D subsidies for new technologies, practices and products connected to the re-use, repair or recycling (etc.) of non-packaging plastics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> decreases the costs of abatement measures triggered by carbon pricing and quota (steps 3 and 4) high approval by stakeholders no regret option innovation takes time
1b	R&D subsidies for innovative bioplastics technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> see above
2	Eco-design criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> stakeholder priority facilitates compliance with quota (step 3) and supports the effectiveness of carbon pricing (step 4)

³ EU COM (2023): Proposal for a Regulation on circularity requirements for vehicle design and on management of end-of-life vehicles, https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-regulation-circularity-requirements-vehicle-design-and-management-end-life-vehicles_en.

Step	Policy instrument	Rationale for selection and order
3	Quota for use of recycled content for producers of non-packaging plastics (e.g., major waste sources such as cars, electrical devices, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> stakeholder priority
4	Carbon price for the use of virgin fossil feedstocks as production input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> stakeholder priority
5	Sustainability criteria for biomass use or carbon price on low-value biomass uses, e.g. from bioenergy and single-use / non-durable bioplastics products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> prerequisite for product subsidy (step 6)
6	Product subsidy for durable non-packaging plastic final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> stakeholder priority supplements R&D support (step 1b) and carbon price (steps 4 and possibly 5)

6.4 Roadmap example: Construction

Similar to other sectors, financial support for innovative materials and construction technologies is a no-regret option to start with (see textiles roadmap). Stakeholder preferences were not consistent between different countries and methods, but direct regulation was generally considered more appropriate or urgent. This includes eco-design criteria for buildings that increase the chances for renovation or recycling. Such criteria at the beginning of the value chain can increase chances for separate waste collection and subsequent reuse and recycling. Therefore, they should be established prior to end-of-life measures such as demolition standards.

Biomass-related policies were also part of stakeholder priorities. Given that biomass has been estimated to account for only 3 % (by mass) of building materials in the EU (Cardellini and Mijndonckx 2022), such policies possibly have a limited impact on the CBBE transition in the construction sector, though. Therefore, they are listed further down on the roadmap. Both a biomass quota and carbon credits for biobased construction materials are among the prioritised policies. Before one of these options is established, sustainability criteria should ensure their

compatibility with environmental targets for biodiversity, soil, and especially carbon storage in forests. In this context, it should be remembered that both biomass quota and carbon credits are unlikely to be cost-efficient and possibly conflict with climate targets in the land use sector (see the biomass paradox in the introductory chapter). These drawbacks and risks should be considered when defining sustainability criteria and in the scope of carbon credits provided to the construction sector.

Turning back to non-renewable construction materials, measures such as eco-design criteria and demolition standards may increase the potential supply of secondary materials. Still, incentives might still be missing to actually use these resources. To create effective demand, other, less popular measures could be necessary. The roadmap, therefore, includes taxing virgin raw materials or construction-related GHG emissions. Given that raw material taxes have a mixed reputation in the EU (Söderholm 2006, 2011) and that the carbon intensity of the linear fossil-based economy is possibly a more pressing issue in times of climate change than the risk of depletion of natural resources (Krautkraemer 2005), stepping up efforts for carbon pricing in the construction sector could be a better solution. This could be achieved by subjecting those construction-related GHG emissions to carbon pricing that are not yet covered by the EU-ETS or similar policies. However, most construction-related GHG emissions are related to energy use and or cement production, both of which are already covered by the EU-ETS. Therefore, it is unclear whether such a step would create substantial additional incentives. These considerations illustrate that the level and nature of incentives to make circular practices competitive in construction require more research and attention from policymakers. Table 5 provides an overview of the roadmap based on currently suggested policies.

Table 5: Exemplary roadmap for the construction sector

Step	Policy instrument	Rationale for selection and order
1	Innovation subsidies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> decreases the costs of abatement measures triggered by biomass quota (step 4) and resource taxes (step 6) high approval by stakeholders no regret option innovation takes time
2	Eco-design criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> stakeholder priority
3	Demolition standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> stakeholder priority
4	Biomass sustainability criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> prerequisite for biomass quota (step 4)
5	Biomass quota or carbon credits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> stakeholder priority
6	Resource or carbon taxes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> complements innovation support (step 1, additional incentives) and eco-design criteria

7. CONCLUSIONS

Creating consistent policies for the CBBE is a complex challenge for policymakers. This task is complicated by various trade-offs and a high risk of unintended side effects. Based on reviewing transition barriers, the creation of a monitoring system, an analysis of CBBE key sectors, the modelling of economic and ecological transition effects, a review of policy options and stakeholder discussions, the following policy recommendations have been derived:

- 1 CBBE transition requires a combination of measures to a) improve the competitiveness of sustainable products, b) provide credible and digestible information and c) target lock-in effects and push technology development.
- 2 The CBBE transition has to be embedded in a clear strategic framework. This framework should specify key characteristics of the future CBBE, such as the desired degree of decoupling. It should also acknowledge unintended side-effects, trade-offs and social challenges, and provide clear answers on how to address these (ensure policy consistency and reliability). Current strategic documents, such as the EU Circular Economy Action Plan or the EU Bioeconomy Strategy, do not sufficiently address these challenges.
- 3 When using direct regulation such as quotas, bans or sustainability criteria, policy makers should
 - 3.1 explore options to limit bureaucratic burdens, e.g., by providing standard values for certain sustainability assessments (similar to standard values in the EU RED for GHG emissions from bioenergy),
 - 3.2 complement quotas, bans, etc., with innovation support to ensure that sufficient sustainable options are available for complying with a quota or to mitigate the negative effects of a ban,
 - 3.3 limit their use to areas where no substantial efficiency losses are to be expected from their application and
 - 3.4 apply them in cases where market-based solutions would intensify social disparities and thus undermine acceptance of the CBBE transition.
- 4 When using market-based instruments such as taxes, tradable permits or subsidies, policy makers should
 - 4.1 complement taxes and tradeable permits with measures that minimise leakage effects, such as carbon border adjustments,
 - 4.2 design innovation subsidies in a way that limits administrative burden for SMEs,
 - 4.3 use, if possible, downstream instead of upstream taxes and
 - 4.4 recycle revenues back to businesses and consumers to improve acceptance.
- 5 To address the trade-off between acceptance by businesses (production costs) and bureaucracy (administrative costs), policymakers should carefully assess when to use market-based policies and when direct regulation is favourable or a useful addition. Potentials of market-based policies to limit administrative costs should be identified and exploited to make the CBBE transition less bureaucratic.
- 6 Regarding individual policy solutions, innovation support, sustainability criteria for material biomass uses and quotas for non-fossil feedstocks are plausible options to accelerate the

transition. In a market-based policy setting, carbon pricing can be an alternative to quotas and sustainability criteria. In the sectors of plastics and chemicals, quotas are possibly more suitable instruments, while carbon pricing may be more effective and efficient in sectors such as textiles and construction.

- 7 The varying degree of progress in the EU member states can justify a customisation of policy measures, such as a variation of targets and quotas, additional support for waste management or restricted support for activities that potentially conflict with environmental targets. Different natural conditions or specialisations in the global economy should be accounted for, though.
- 8 Effects of the CBBE transition on economic growth should be monitored closely. Negative impacts may require macroeconomic policy strategies such as temporary increases in public spending. Intensified innovation support, broader measures of welfare and strategic marketing efforts can help to offset these impacts.
- 9 To mitigate trade-offs related to the use of biomass (land area), increasing demand for this resource could be met by designating priority areas for additional biomass production. Such priority areas should be characterised by simultaneously low economic and ecological value or allow for win-win solutions regarding biomass production and the environment. In addition to this, potential to increase overall land use efficiency should be identified and exploited.
- 10 The CBBE transition should be targeted at the EU level to create markets that are large enough to support sustainable business models. To facilitate the transition in the labour market, targeted educational measures should be implemented that qualify people for positions in new industries or services. Standards regulating these new sectors should be reassessed in order to ensure equal or better income and working conditions.

Further insights on CBBE transition policies can be found in the joint policy recommendations from the EU projects BIOTRANSFORM, ROBIN, BIOMODEL4REGIONS and SUSTRACK⁴.

⁴ <https://www.biotransform-project.eu/news-events/news/66-joint-policy-recommendations-for-the-transition-to-circular-bioeconomy-in-eu-regions-and-cities>

ANNEX I - SUSTRACK POLICY FACTSHEETS

TEXTILES

Policy set: Direct regulation

	Biomass	Circularity
Promoting transition	<p>Quota for use of bio-based (and recycled) feedstock in textile production and imports</p> <p>Public procurement of textiles without fossil-based content</p>	<p>Quota for use of recycled (and bio-based) material in textiles production and imports</p> <p>Eco-design criteria for mandatory durability, repairability and recyclability standards (incl. for imports)</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the quota, public procurement (e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive)</p>	<p>Ban on Destruction of Unsold Goods (Existing EU instrument) as part of polluter pays principle to discourage overproduction</p>

Policy set: Market-based instruments

	Biomass	Circularity
Promoting transition	<p>Innovation subsidy</p> <p>for developing new technologies and practices for bio-based textiles including support for market penetration of innovative products</p>	<p>Innovation subsidy</p> <p>for innovative textile reuse or recycling practices and technologies, including support for market penetration of innovative products</p> <p>“Green VAT”</p> <p>Reduced Value-Added Tax on re-used or recycled textiles</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Environmental tax</p> <p>on “fast fashion” textiles, fibers, yarns and fabrics e.g., including for non-sustainable cotton products to limit waste and pollution</p>	<p>Carbon tax</p> <p>on use of fossil feedstocks in textiles production</p>

PLASTICS

Policy set: Direct regulation

	Biomass	Circularity
Promoting transition	<p>Product subsidy</p> <p>paid to producers of durable non-packaging plastic final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria</p>	<p>Quota</p> <p>for use of recycled content for producers or commercial users of non-packaging plastics (e.g., major waste sources such as cars, electrical devices etc.)</p> <p>Eco-design criteria</p> <p>for non-packaging plastic products to improve ease of repair, recycling etc.</p> <p>Public procurement</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Sustainability criteria</p> <p>for receiving the product subsidy. E.g., mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas with high carbon or biodiversity value, restriction to durable products etc.</p> <p>Additional: Cap</p> <p>for share or total quantity of biomass used in the sector</p>	<p>Product bans</p> <p>of additional single-use and short-life plastic products or product parts where sustainable and low-cost alternatives incl. reuse and repair are available</p>

Policy set: Market-based instruments

	Biomass	Circularity
Promoting transition	<p>Innovation subsidy</p> <p>for new bioplastics technologies and for innovative durable bioplastic products to support their market penetration</p>	<p>Innovation subsidy</p> <p>for new technologies, practices and products connected to the re-use, repair or recycling (etc.) of non-packaging plastics</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Carbon price</p> <p>on emissions from low-value biomass uses, e.g. from bioenergy and single-use / non-durable bioplastics products.</p> <p><i>This policy instrument should be combined with a carbon price on fossil feedstock use, see next column.</i></p>	<p>Carbon price</p> <p>for use of fossil feedstocks as production input, to be paid by producers of non-packaging plastics</p>

CHEMICALS

Policy set: Direct regulation/Mixed-policy approach

	Direct regulation	Mixed-policy approach	Direct regulation
	Biomass/GHG reduction		Circularity/Toxicity
Promoting transition	<p>Quota</p> <p>for non-fossil feedstock shares in chemicals production - leading to phase out of fossil feedstocks, e.g. in 2050</p> <p>Additional: innovation subsidies</p> <p>for development and market penetration of non-fossil chemicals</p>	<p>Product subsidy</p> <p>for non-fossil chemicals, for example “green VAT” (reduced Value-Added Tax)</p> <p>Additional: phase out</p> <p>of fossil feedstocks leading to a final ban, e.g. in 2050</p>	<p>Innovation subsidy</p> <p>for developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD*-framework and decontamination technologies</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Sustainability criteria</p> <p>for biomass to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Materials Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive)</p>	<p>Sustainability criteria</p> <p>for biomass to be eligible to the subsidy (e.g., Renewable Materials Directive following the Renewable Energy Directive)</p>	<p>Thresholds</p> <p>for key Substances of Concern in products that inhibit reuse, recycling etc.</p> <p>SCIP Extension</p> <p>Extension of EU SCIP database to chemicals inhibiting circularity</p> <p>REACH: extended criteria</p> <p>for chemicals permission that consider recycling, reuse etc. of products</p>

*: Safe and Sustainable by Design

Policy set: Market-based instruments

	Biomass/GHG reduction	Circularity/Toxicity
Promoting transition	<p>Innovation subsidy for innovative non-fossil chemicals, including supporting market penetration of novel products</p>	<p>Innovation subsidy For developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD*-framework and decontamination technologies</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Carbon tax for fossil feedstocks in chemicals production and for low-value biomass uses</p>	<p>Pollution tax on key Substances of Concern that pose major risks to health or environment and thus inhibit circularity (e.g., lead, PFAS, flame retardants)</p>

*: Safe and Sustainable by Design

CONSTRUCTION

Policy set: Direct regulation

	Biomass	Circularity
Promoting transition	<p>Quota/target</p> <p>for use of bio-based material in new buildings including higher targets for public procurement</p>	<p>Quota/target</p> <p>for use of recycled materials in new buildings</p> <p>Ecodesign criteria</p> <p>For building companies on design, construction and use of materials. Aim should be to design for reuse, disassembly, physical durability, adaptability and repair and minimising material intensity.</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Sustainability criteria</p> <p>for biomass to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive)</p> <p>Subsidy</p> <p>for refurbishment of buildings</p>	<p>Demolition Standards</p> <p>Requirements for the demolition of buildings, that increase chances for re-use, upcycling and recycling of materials, and thus encourage waste reduction and possibly refurbishment</p>

Policy set: Market-based instruments

	Biomass	Circularity
Promoting transition	<p>Innovation subsidy</p> <p>for development and uses of innovative bio-based construction materials</p>	<p>Innovation subsidy</p> <p>for innovative circular technologies or practices (e.g., use of recycled materials)</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Carbon tax</p> <p>on all lifecycle GHG emissions of building materials that are NOT part of current carbon pricing (EU-ETS I+II) including the carbon content of short-life biomass materials</p> <p>Carbon credit / subsidy</p> <p>Bio-based building materials that ensure long-term storage of carbon (e.g., 50+ years) are exempt from the tax and receive a credit / subsidy</p>	<p>Material tax</p> <p>on the use of virgin raw materials for construction (e.g., gravel, stone, sand) including imports</p>

REFERENCES

- Aalbers, Rob; Shestalova, Victoria; Kocsis, Viktória (2013): Innovation policy for directing technical change in the power sector. In *Energy Policy* 63, pp. 1240-1250. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2013.09.013.
- Aidt, Toke; Jia, Lili; Low, Hamish (2017): Are prices enough? The economics of material demand reduction. In *Philosophical transactions. Series A, Mathematical, physical, and engineering sciences* 375 (2016). DOI: 10.1098/rsta.2016.0370.
- Ayres, Robert; van den Bergh, Jeroen; Gowdy, John (2001): Strong versus Weak Sustainability. In *Environmental Ethics* 23 (2), pp. 155-168. DOI: 10.5840/enviroethics200123225.
- Batie, Sandra S. (2008): Wicked Problems and Applied Economics. In *American J Agri Economics* 90 (5), pp. 1176-1191. DOI: 10.1111/j.1467-8276.2008.01202.x.
- Baumol, William J. (1977): On recycling as a moot environmental issue. In *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management* 4 (1), pp. 83-87. DOI: 10.1016/0095-0696(77)90017-1.
- Baumol, William J.; Oates, Wallace E. (1971): The Use of Standards and Prices for Protection of the Environment. In *The Swedish Journal of Economics* 73 (1), p. 42. DOI: 10.2307/3439132.
- Baumol, William J.; Oates, Wallace E. (2005): The theory of environmental policy. 2. ed., repr., transf. to digital printing. Cambridge: Cambridge Univ. Press.
- Bertram, Christoph; Luderer, Gunnar; Pietzcker, Robert C.; Schmid, Eva; Kriegler, Elmar; Edenhofer, Ottmar (2015): Complementing carbon prices with technology policies to keep climate targets within reach. In *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 5 (3), pp. 235-239. DOI: 10.1038/nclimate2514.
- Braathen, Nils Axel (2007): Instrument Mixes for Environmental Policy: How Many Stones Should be Used to Kill a Bird? In *International Review of Environmental and Resource Economics* 1 (2), pp. 185-235. DOI: 10.1561/101.00000005.
- Cardellini, Giuseppe; Mijndonckx, Joren (2022): Synergies, energy efficiency and circularity in the renovation wave - bio-based products for the renovation wave.
- Cludius, Johanna; Duscha, Vicky; Friedrichsen, Nele; Schumacher, Katja (2019): Cost-efficiency of the EU Emissions Trading System: An Evaluation of the Second Trading Period. In *EEEP* 8 (1). DOI: 10.5547/2160-5890.8.1.jclu.
- Cowie, Annette L.; Berndes, Göran; Bentsen, Niclas Scott; Brandão, Miguel; Cherubini, Francesco; Egnell, Gustaf et al. (2021): Applying a science-based systems perspective to dispel misconceptions about climate effects of forest bioenergy. In *GCB Bioenergy* 13 (8), pp. 1210-1231. DOI: 10.1111/gcbb.12844.
- DEHSt (2025): 2023 Emission Situation in National Emissions Trading System (nEHS). Berlin. Available online at https://www.dehst.de/SharedDocs/downloads/EN/nehs/emission-situation-2023.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=6.
- Elbersen, B., Eupan, V., Meijinger, W., & Mantel, S. (2025). Marginal land Classification and Information System (MIDAS-MLCIS 1) for low ILUC feedstock and current and future expectations

on soil erosion, water stress and ecosystem services conditions. Deliverable 1.1. MIDAS project. GA No. 101082070. Wageningen: MIDAS.

European Commission (2025): The future of European competitiveness. Part A: A competitiveness strategy for Europe. Luxembourg: Publications Office.

Fischer, Aglaia; Pascucci, Stefano (2017): Institutional incentives in circular economy transition: The case of material use in the Dutch textile industry. In *Journal of Cleaner Production* 155, pp. 17-32. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.038.

Fischer, Carolyn; Preonas, Louis; Newell, Richard G. (2017): Environmental and Technology Policy Options in the Electricity Sector: Are We Deploying Too Many? In *Journal of the Association of Environmental and Resource Economists* 4 (4), pp. 959-984. DOI: 10.1086/692507.

Fullerton, Don (2011): Six distributional effects of environmental policy. In *Risk analysis : an official publication of the Society for Risk Analysis* 31 (6), pp. 923-929. DOI: 10.1111/j.1539-6924.2011.01628.x.

Gaudet, Gérard (2007): Natural resource economics under the rule of Hotelling. In *Canadian Journal of Economics/Revue canadienne d'économique* 40 (4), pp. 1033-1059. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.00441.x.

Grizzetti, B.; Lanza, D.; Liqueste, C.; Reynaud, A.; Cardoso, A. C. (2016): Assessing water ecosystem services for water resource management. In *Environmental Science & Policy* 61, pp. 194-203. DOI: 10.1016/j.envsci.2016.04.008.

Guyomard, H.; Bouamra-Mechemache, Z.; Chatellier, V.; Delaby, L.; Détang-Dessendre, C.; Peyraud, J-L; Réquillart, V. (2021): Review: Why and how to regulate animal production and consumption: The case of the European Union. In *Animal : an international journal of animal bioscience* 15 Suppl 1, p. 100283. DOI: 10.1016/j.animal.2021.100283.

Haites, Erik (2018): Carbon taxes and greenhouse gas emissions trading systems: what have we learned? In *Climate Policy* 18 (8), pp. 955-966. DOI: 10.1080/14693062.2018.1492897.

Hoogmartens, Rob; Eyckmans, Johan; van Passel, Steven (2018): A Hotelling model for the circular economy including recycling, substitution and waste accumulation. In *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 128, pp. 98-109. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.09.015.

Hu, Junhui; Jåstad, Eirik Ogner; Rørstad, Per Kristian (2025): Exploring trade-offs in forest carbon storage: A cost-effectiveness study of Nordic forests and harvested wood products. In *Forest Policy and Economics* 179, p. 103619. DOI: 10.1016/j.forpol.2025.103619.

Hurmekoski, Elias; Kunttu, Janni; Heinonen, Tero; Pukkala, Timo; Peltola, Heli (2023): Does expanding wood use in construction and textile markets contribute to climate change mitigation? In *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 174, p. 113152. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2023.113152.

Jaffe, Adam B.; Newell, Richard G.; Stavins, Robert N. (2005): A tale of two market failures: Technology and environmental policy. In *Ecological Economics* 54 (2-3), pp. 164-174. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2004.12.027.

Johansson, Nils (2023): Recycling warning! Reconfiguring the toxic politics of a circular economy. In *Sustain Sci* 18 (2), pp. 1043-1048. DOI: 10.1007/s11625-022-01220-0.

- Jonsson, Ragnar; Rinaldi, Francesca; Pilli, Roberto; Fiorese, Giulia; Hurmekoski, Elias; Cazzaniga, Noemi et al. (2021): Boosting the EU forest-based bioeconomy: Market, climate, and employment impacts. In *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 163, p. 120478. DOI: 10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120478.
- Kalkuhl, Matthias; Edenhofer, Ottmar; Lessmann, Kai (2013): Renewable energy subsidies: Second-best policy or fatal aberration for mitigation? In *Resource and Energy Economics* 35 (3), pp. 217-234. DOI: 10.1016/j.reseneeco.2013.01.002.
- Kim, Bae-Geun (2020): Sectoral shifts and comovements in employment. In: *Economics Letters* 192, 109208, DOI: 10.1016/j.econlet.2020.109208.
- Kinnaman, Thomas C.; Shinkuma, Takayoshi; Yamamoto, Masashi (2014): The socially optimal recycling rate: Evidence from Japan. In *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management* 68 (1), pp. 54-70. DOI: 10.1016/j.jeem.2014.01.004.
- Kirchherr, Julian; Reike, Denise; Hekkert, Marko (2017): Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. In *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 127, pp. 221-232. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.09.005.
- Krautkraemer, Jeffrey A. (2005): Economics of Natural Resource Scarcity: The State of the Debate: Unknown. Available online at <https://ageconsearch.umn.edu/record/10562/>.
- Kronenberg, Tobias (2008): SHOULD WE WORRY ABOUT THE FAILURE OF THE HOTELLING RULE? In *Journal of Economic Surveys* 22 (4), pp. 774-793. DOI: 10.1111/j.1467-6419.2008.00549.x.
- Kubiszewski, Ida; Costanza, Robert; Franco, Carol; Lawn, Philip; Talberth, John; Jackson, Tim; Aylmer, Camille (2013): Beyond GDP: Measuring and achieving global genuine progress. In *Ecological Economics* 93, pp. 57-68. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2013.04.019.
- Lintunen, Jussi; Uusivuori, Jussi (2016): On the economics of forests and climate change: Deriving optimal policies. In *JFE* 24, pp. 130-156. DOI: 10.1016/j.jfe.2016.05.001.
- Lundgren, Tommy (2008): The Economics of Biofuels. In *IRERE* 2 (3), pp. 237-280. DOI: 10.1561/101.00000017.
- Marschinski, Robert; Quirion, Philippe (2014): Tradable Renewable Quota vs. Feed-In Tariff vs. Feed-In Premium Under Uncertainty. In *SSRN Journal*. DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.2532391.
- Merfort, Leon; Bauer, Nico; Humpenöder, Florian; Klein, David; Strefler, Jessica; Popp, Alexander et al. (2021): Bioenergy-induced land-use change emissions with sectorally fragmented policies.
- Miettinen, Jenni; Ollikainen, Markku (2024): The impacts of climate and energy policy instruments on forest bioeconomy. In *Forest Policy and Economics* 169, p. 103338. DOI: 10.1016/j.forpol.2024.103338.
- Neumayer, Eric (2013): Weak versus strong sustainability. Exploring the limits of two opposing paradigms. Fourth edition. Cheltenham, UK, Northampton, MA, USA: Edward Elgar.
- Philippidis, George; M'Barek, Robert; Urban-Boysen, Kirsten; van Zeist, Willem-Jan (2023): Exploring economy-wide sustainable conditions for EU bio-chemical activities. In *Ecological Economics* 210, p. 107857. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2023.107857.

Powers, Melissa (2016): Lessons from US biofuels policy: the Renewable Fuel Standard's rocky ride. In Yves Le Bouthillier, Annette Cowie, Paul Martin, Heather McLeod-Kilmurray (Eds.): *The law and policy of biofuels*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing (The IUCN academy of environmental law series).

Purkus, Alexandra (2016): Concepts and instruments for a rational bioenergy policy. A new institutional economics approach. Cham: Springer (Lecture notes in energy, volume 55).

Rosenow, Jan; Fawcett, Tina; Eyre, Nick; Oikonomou, Vlasia (2016): Energy efficiency and the policy mix. In *Building Research & Information* 44 (5-6), pp. 562-574. DOI: 10.1080/09613218.2016.1138803.

Schindler, Harry; Majer, Stefan; Thrän, Daniela; Lenz, Volker (2024): Sustainable forest bioenergy: DBFZ Deutsches Biomasseforschungszentrum gemeinnützige GmbH.

Schulte, Maximilian; Jonsson, Ragnar; Hammar, Torun; Stendahl, Johan; Hansson, Per-Anders (2022): Nordic forest management towards climate change mitigation: time dynamic temperature change impacts of wood product systems including substitution effects. In *Eur J Forest Res* 141 (5), pp. 845-863. DOI: 10.1007/s10342-022-01477-1.

Slunge, Daniel; Alpizar, Francisco (2019): Market-Based Instruments for Managing Hazardous Chemicals: A Review of the Literature and Future Research Agenda. In *Sustainability* 11 (16), p. 4344. DOI: 10.3390/su11164344.

Söderholm, Patrik (2006): Environmental taxation in the natural resource extraction sector: is it a good idea? In *Eur. Env.* 16 (4), pp. 232-245. DOI: 10.1002/eet.415.

Söderholm, Patrik (2011): Taxing virgin natural resources: Lessons from aggregates taxation in Europe. In *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 55 (11), pp. 911-922. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2011.05.011.

Stern, Nicholas (2007): *The economics of climate change. The Stern review*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Tian, Xi; Gao, Wenwen; Liu, Yaobin; Xu, Ming (2020): Secondary resource curse's formation and transmission mechanism based on environmental externality theory. In *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 161, p. 104958. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104958.

Tietenberg, Tom (1995): Tradeable permits for pollution control when emission location matters: What have we learned? In *Environ Resource Econ* 5 (2), pp. 95-113. DOI: 10.1007/BF00693018.

van den Bergh, Jeroen C.J.M. (2013): Environmental and climate innovation: Limitations, policies and prices. In *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 80 (1), pp. 11-23. DOI: 10.1016/j.techfore.2012.08.004.

van Kooten, G. Cornelis; Binkley, Clark S.; Delcourt, Gregg (1995): Effect of Carbon Taxes and Subsidies on Optimal Forest Rotation Age and Supply of Carbon Services. In *American J Agri Economics* 77 (2), pp. 365-374. DOI: 10.2307/1243546.

Zibunas, Christian; Meys, Raoul; Kätelhön, Arne; Bardow, André (2022): Cost-optimal pathways towards net-zero chemicals and plastics based on a circular carbon economy. In *Computers & Chemical Engineering* 162, p. 107798. DOI: 10.1016/j.compchemeng.2022.107798.

Zink, Trevor; Geyer, Roland (2017): Circular Economy Rebound. In *J of Industrial Ecology* 21 (3), pp. 593-602. DOI: 10.1111/jiec.12545.

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